

Research Article

Revolutionizing Culinary Education through Innovation: The Culinary Knife Cut Assistant (CKCA)

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Abstract: Mastering knife skills is essential in culinary education, but many students find this aspect particularly difficult to master. The Culinary Knife Cut Assistant is a new teaching and learning tool designed to help students better understand and perform basic vegetable cutting techniques as required by Western culinary standards. This tool offers a visual and hands-on reference, allowing learners to recognize, remember, and accurately reproduce standard vegetable cuts. It aims to address common problems, such as inconsistent cutting, confusion over technical terminology, and food waste during practice sessions. The Culinary Knife Cut Assistant serves as a bridge between theory and practice, acting as an interactive reference in the culinary lab that supports stronger retention, skill development, and student confidence. The main goals of this tool are to (1) create an effective and engaging environment for learning knife skills, (2) improve accuracy and consistency in culinary training, and (3) reduce food waste and associated costs due to repeated mistakes. With its use, students are expected to become more competent, instructors can teach more efficiently, and culinary education can become more sustainable. Overall, the Culinary Knife Cut Assistant represents a step forward in culinary teaching by combining technology with practical learning.

Keywords: culinary education; knife skills; teaching and learning tool; innovation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Knife skills are among the most fundamental competencies in culinary education. Mastery of basic vegetable cutting techniques, such as *batonnet*, *julienne*, *jardinière*, *brunoise*, and *paysanne*, is critical

for students pursuing culinary arts, gastronomy, and food preparation. However, teaching and learning these skills present significant challenges (Scott & Husain, 2021). Students usually struggle to visualize the correct size and form of each cut, leading to inconsistent results, increased food wastage, and additional costs during training (McArthur-Floyd et al., 2023).

To deal with these challenges, the *Culinary Knife Cut Assistant (CKCA)* is introduced as an innovative teaching and learning tool. This product is designed to provide a visual and accurate reference for students, making it easier for them to understand, practice, and have a knife skills according to professional culinary standards. Despite repeated demonstrations by instructors, many students fail to produce accurate cuts due to limited visualization, insufficient practice time, and difficulty memorizing technical terms and measurements. This problem affects not only student learning outcomes but also instructional efficiency and resource management. Traditional teaching relies heavily on textbooks and live demonstrations, which may not be sufficient for kinesthetic learners who benefit from hands-on, guided practice (Abadi Simamora et al., 2025). Therefore, there is a need for a creative educational tool that bridges the gap between theory and practice, ensuring students achieve competency while reducing material wastage.

The objective of this innovation are to provide a specialized reference tool for culinary labs and kitchens to enhance teaching and learning processes. Second, to help in improving students' understanding, accuracy, and consistency in executing fundamental vegetable cuts and lastly to reduce cutting errors and food wastage, thus saving costs in culinary training.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The *Culinary Knife Cut Assistant (CKCA)* was developed as a teaching and learning aid specifically designed for use during practical culinary classes. The challenges of inefficiency and inconsistency in achieving accurate vegetable cut sizes inspired the creation of the CKCA — a ruler-like tool enriched with detailed information and visual guides to assist both instructors and students in mastering fundamental cutting techniques.

Figure 1. The design of Culinary Knife Cut Assistant (CKCA)

The design of the CKCA emphasizes practicality, accuracy, and visual clarity to support experiential learning in culinary education. It is modelled after a measuring tool but enhanced with detailed visual guides, standardized dimensions, and labels representing various classical Western vegetable cuts such as *batonnet*, *julienne*, *jardinière*, *brunoise*, *paysanne* and other cuts. This dual function — as both a ruler and a visual learning device — enables students to directly compare their actual cuts with the standardized sizes showed on the CKCA. The CKCA is made from a transparent acrylic

material known for its durability and clarity with specific thickness. This see-through feature allows students to easily measure their cuts by providing real-size measurements and a precise grid layout similar to a ruler, ensuring accuracy and ease of use during practical sessions.

The product was conceptualized through observations of repeated challenges in the teaching and learning of knife skills, where students often face difficulties in visualizing correct dimensions and maintaining consistency. By integrating visual references and measurement scales into a single, easy-to-use tool, the CKCA bridges the gap between theoretical and hands-on practice.

Figure 2. The comparison between regular ruler and CKCA in vegetable cutting.

3. CONCLUSION

The *Culinary Knife Cut Assistant* (CKCA) offers a practical, innovative solution to one of the most persistent challenges in culinary education: mastering fundamental knife cuts. By combining experiential learning with a tangible teaching tool, this innovation has the potential to improve student performance, enhance teaching effectiveness, and reduce resource wastage (Javed, 2023). This paper highlights the relevance of integrating educational tools into culinary pedagogy, paving the way for more efficient and impactful teaching and learning practices in gastronomy and food preparation.

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